

Scores from inter-rater tests similar to those shown in Table 2 except that both positive predictions and negative predictions were compared between each individual LUCA study and the consensus of the other seven LUCA studies.

	Harris	Mirkin	Delaye	Yang	Ranea	Wang	Srinivasan	Weiss
%, 2	1.00	0.98	0.96	0.99	1.00	0.93	0.98	0.99
%, 3	0.99	0.97	0.95	0.98	0.99	0.92	0.97	0.99
%, 4	0.98	0.96	0.94	0.97	0.98	0.91	0.96	0.98
%, 5	0.97	0.95	0.93	0.96	0.97	0.90	0.95	0.96
α/π^* , 2	0.97	0.51	0.03	0.68	0.95	-1.00	0.41	0.78
α/π^* , 3	0.85	0.28	-0.20	0.45	0.83	-1.33	0.19	0.62
α/π^* , 4	0.54	-0.01	-0.47	0.15	0.54	-1.62	-0.08	0.33
α/π^* , 5	0.08	-0.30	-0.71	-0.16	0.11	-1.72	-0.36	-0.05